

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

The role of surfactants in preserving the stability of amorphous solid dispersions: A review

Prashanth Parupathi ^{1,*} and Siddharatha Dhoppalapudi ²

¹ Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences, ST. Peter's Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Hanamkonda, Telangana, India 506001.

² Department of Analytical Research & Development. Hikma Pharmaceuticals, Columbus, Ohio 43228, USA.

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Abstract

In recent years among various formulation strategies, amorphous solid dispersions (ASDs) has gained tremendous recognition for improving the solubility of poorly soluble drug substances. Among various manufacturing strategies, hot melt extrusion (HME), spray drying, kinetisol, and electrospinning are the most widely employed for developing ASDs. Despite the improving solubility and bioavailability, the stability of ASDs is the major problem haunting the pharmaceutical industries. Various factors, such as miscibility, the solubility of the drug in polymer, drug-polymer interactions, glass transition temperature, hygroscopicity, and storage conditions, determine the stability of ASDs. The poor stability of amorphous drugs also limits the drug loading capacity, resulting in an increased volume of the dosage form affecting patient compliance. Apart from the physical stability of ASDs, solution-mediated recrystallization of the drug when present in a supersaturated state is another factor affecting the quality and performance of the formulations. In recent years incorporation of surfactants to hinder solution-mediated recrystallization of drugs, thereby improving the stability and performance of ASD formulations, is being most widely investigated. The incorporation of surfactant in the HME process will also act as a plasticizer, thereby allowing the process to be carried at lower temperatures. This review article mainly focuses on the role of surfactants in ASD systems and recent advancements. Still, research is warranted to understand the mechanism of surfactants and to establish screening criteria.

Keywords: Amorphous solid dispersions; Hot melt extrusion; Spray drying; Kinetisol; Surfactant; Poor solubility

1. Introduction

In today's world, the main focus of the pharmaceutical industry lies in improving the solubility and bioavailability of poorly soluble drug substances. Around 60-70% of the new chemical entities (NCEs) within the developmental pipeline are claimed to be poorly soluble, belonging to the biological classification system (BCS) class II and IV [1–6]. The poor solubility of drug substance will affect the bioavailability and therefore require the administration of larger therapeutic doses to achieve the required pharmacological action. Knowledge of solubility will not only help the design of dosage forms but will also provide information for developing liquid formulations required for toxicological and pharmacokinetic studies. In addition, it will also aid the process of analytical method development, which requires the knowledge of drug solubility for developing a robust analytical method [7–12]. Thus, improving solubility is the major prerequisite for the developmental scientist and is one of the major physicochemical properties affecting *in vivo* performance.

Among various dosage forms such as injectables and transdermal medications, oral formulations has huge demand attributing to various advantages in terms of business activity and patient compliance. The oral medications are cost-

* Corresponding author Prashanth Parupathi

Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences, ST. Peter's Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Hanamkonda, Telangana, India 506001.

effective and easy to administer when compared with the medications intended for other routes. Among various oral dosage forms such as liquids and solids, the solid dosage forms (capsules and tablets) have huge demand attributed to their longer shelf life and easy transportation [13–20]. Among tablets and capsules, the tablets are mostly preferred attributing to this low manufacturing cost and no possibility of adulteration. In addition, the tablets provide the flexibility of dose division for the pediatric patient population. The division of dose remains impossible for capsule dosage forms and making them prone to adulteration. Thus, owing to the advantages of oral medications, the pharmaceutical industries are left with no choice of improving the solubility of drug substances.

For the last three decades, various formulation approaches such as self-emulsifying drug delivery systems (SEDDS), liposomes, pro-liposomes, complexation, salts, cocrystals, prodrugs, amorphous solid dispersions, solid crystal suspensions, and co-amorphous systems have been investigated for improving the solubility of drug substances. The low oral bioavailability can be due to poor solubility or poor absorption of the drugs. The bioavailability of the drug substances experiencing solubility as a rate-limiting step can be improved by employing suitable solubility enhancement approaches [21–26]. In the case of drug substances experiencing poor absorption or permeability across the biological membrane, the bioavailability can be improved by employing permeation enhancers. Among the various formulation strategies, amorphous solid dispersions (ASDs) have gained tremendous recognition and attention from researchers across the pharmaceutical industries and regulatory bodies. Within ASDs, the drug loses its crystal habitat and exists in a molecularly dispersed high-energy state, resulting in improved wettability and solubility. Various manufacturing techniques such as high shear granulation, fluid bed granulation, hot melt extrusion (HME), spray drying, and Kinetisol have been investigated for developing ASDs. Among various manufacturing strategies, the HME and spray drying process has gained commercial viability for manufacturing ASDs [23, 27–58]. To date, there have been various products launched into the market which are manufactured by these techniques and are listed in Table 1. This review article mainly focuses on the role of surfactants in improving the stability of ASDs, along with a note on the advantages and limitations of ASDs.

Table 1 Various commercial ASD formulations [45]

Trade Name	Drug Substance	Year of Approval
Isoptin® SR	Verapamil	1987
NuvaRing®	Etonogestrel/Ethinyl Estradiol	2001
Kaletra®	Lopinavir/Ritonavir	2007
Norvir®	Ritonavir	2010
Onmel®	Itraconazole	2010
Noxafil®	Posaconazole	2013
Belsomra®	Suvorexant	2014
Viekira® XR	Dasabuvir/Ombitasvir/Paritaprevir/Ritonair	2014
Venclexta®	Venetoclax	2016
Mavyret®	Glecaprevir/Pibrentasvir	2017
Lynparza®	Olaparib	2018
Braftovi®	Encorafenib	2020
Oriahnn®	Elagolix/Estradiol/Norethindrone Acetate	2020

2. Factors affecting the stability of ASDs

The ASDs are identified as a commercially viable approach for improving the solubility of poorly water-soluble drug substances. Within ASDs, the drug substance exists in a molecularly dispersed high-energy state. Over some time, the mobility of the drug molecules will increase and results in the recrystallization of the drug affecting the stability and performance of the formulation. Various factors, such as storage conditions, atmospheric humidity, glass transition temperature, miscibility, and drug-polymer interactions, play an important role in preserving the stability of ASD systems. In order to develop a stable ASD system, the drug and polymer need to be miscible, resulting in the formation

of a single-phase system with one glass transition temperature. If the concentration of the drug is maintained above the miscibility levels, the mobility of the drug upon storage will increase, leading to recrystallization [59–68]. The formation of drug-polymer interaction will hinder the mobility of the drug inside the polymeric carrier, thereby improving the shelf life of the product. The storage temperature needs to be maintained below the glass transition temperature of the ASD system since storage of formulation above the glass transition will trigger mobility and recrystallization. The formulations of ASDs need to be protected from environmental moisture since the moisture acts as a plasticizer and results in reduced glass transition temperature of the system. The utmost care must be taken while milling the ASDs since the generated heat affects the glass transition temperature resulting in mobility and recrystallization of the drug.

Figure 1 Factors influencing the stability of ASD systems

2.1. Role of surfactants

Figure 2 Schematic representation of the role of surfactant

The ASD systems are also prone to solution-mediated recrystallization of drugs when brought in contact with bulk dissolution media. When an ASD system is brought in contact with dissolution media, the drug might exist in a supersaturation state resulting in the recrystallization of the drug affecting the solubility and performance of the product. Thus incorporation of surfactant into the dissolution media or into the ASD system improves the stability and performance of the formulation. The surfactants, when added above the critical micellar concentration (CMC), result in the formation of the micellar system, thereby entrapping the amorphous drug and preventing recrystallization. The miscibility of the surfactant in the presence of drug and polymer needs to be evaluated for developing a robust formulation [69–80]. The miscibility can be evaluated by employing a thermal characterization technique, i.e.,

differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). The glass transition temperature of the ternary system (drug, polymer, and surfactant) needs to be monitored since the majority of the surfactants are low melting point materials and result in lower glass transition of the ASD systems. In addition, the surfactants will also help lower the processing temperatures, thereby exposing the formulation components to lower temperatures when processed by HME technology. A few case studies involving the investigation of the surfactant's role in preserving and improving the stability of ASD systems are discussed below.

3. Case studies

Shrawan Baghel et al. (2018) [81] investigated the role of surfactants in developing ASDs by spray drying. Dipyridamole and cinnarizine were selected as model drugs. Polyvinyl pyrrolidone K30 and hydroxypropyl methylcellulose K100 (HPMC) were selected as polymeric carriers. Sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) and poloxamer 188 were employed as surfactants. The formulations of drug-polymer; drug-polymer-polymer; drug-polymer-surfactant; and drug-polymer-polymer-surfactant were manufactured by spray drying approach by dissolving in a 1:1 ratio of dichloromethane and ethanol. The drug load was maintained at 20%w/w for all the investigated formulations, and the surfactant concentration was maintained at 5%w/w. The spray drying process was performed using a 0.2 mm size of nozzle at a 6 mL/min of flow rate by maintaining an inlet temperature of 80 °C. Upon investigating the developed formulations for *in vitro* drug release profiles, the formulations free of surfactant were able to maintain the supersaturation state of the drug compared with the surfactant-based formulations. The incorporation of surfactant has affected the drug-polymer interactions, thereby promoting the recrystallization of the drug. Thus drug-polymer interactions also need to be considered for developing stable ASD formulations.

Clara E Correa Soto et al. (2022) [82] have investigated the role of various surfactants (cationic, anionic, and non-ionic) on the stability and release profiles of ASDs developed by rotaflash evaporation technique. The formulations were developed with drug load ranging between 40-60 %w/w, and the surfactant concentration was maintained identically at 5 %w/w for all the investigated formulations. The formulation components were dissolved in methanol and subjected to rotaflash evaporation by maintaining a water batch temperature of 50 °C. Clopidogrel was selected as a model hydrophobic drug candidate, and Kollidon VA 64 was employed as a polymeric carrier. A wide variety of surfactants such as SDS, cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB), Tween 80, and tocopherol polyethylene glycol 1000 succinate (TPGS) have been investigated. Among all the investigated formulations, SDS at 5 %w/w of concentration was able to maintain the stability and supersaturation state up to a drug loading of 50 %w/w. This shows the importance of screening suitable type of surfactant for developing ASD systems.

Tanvi M Deshpande et al. (2018) [83] investigated the role of sodium lauryl sulfate (SLS) and TPGS in improving the stability of itraconazole-based ASDs developed by the spray drying approach. Various polymers HPMC E50 LV, PVP K30, Kollidon VA 64, Soluplus, HPMCAS-HF, Eudragit L100-55, and PEG 4000, have been investigated for developing ASDs. All the formulations were investigated for a drug load of 50 %w/w, and the drug solution was prepared for a solid content of 10% in a 2:1 ratio of methylene chloride and methanol. The process of spray drying was performed at 80 °C of inlet temperature and 12 mL/min of feed rate. Among all the investigated formulations, the binary ASDs of the drug and HPMCAS-HF were found to be stable and able to maintain the supersaturation state of the drug with no recrystallization. The formulations of ternary ASD dispersions were found to be unstable, attributing to the competition between drug and surfactant for the binding sites of the polymer. Thus incorporation of surfactant into the binary ASD system will not improve the stability of the formulations in all cases.

Schittny A et al., (2020) [84] investigated the role of surfactants in combination when employed in the ASD system. Efavirenz was selected as a model drug, and the ASDs were developed for a drug load of 20-30 %w/w using hydroxypropyl methylcellulose phthalate (HPMCP) HP50 and HP55 as base polymer by HME process. Upon investigation of the developed formulations, the ASDs with a combination of sucrose palmitate and polysorbate 80 as surfactants have influenced the drug release kinetics and maintained the supersaturation state of the drug. The *in vivo* characterization of the formulations in rates has resulted in improved bioavailability when compared with the pure drug and binary ASD system with drug and polymer. This shows the importance of surfactants in maintaining stability and improving the *in vivo* performance when administered orally.

Anura S Indulkar et al., (2022) [85] investigated the roles of various surfactants on the release profiles and stability of ASDs developed for ritonavir drug using copovidone as a polymeric carrier by rotaflash evaporation. Span 85, TPGS, Span 20, Tween 80, and SDS were selected as polymeric carriers. The formulations were investigated for a drug load of 30 %w/w and 5 %w/w of surfactant. The solutions for rotaflash evaporation are prepared by dissolving the physical mixtures in dichloromethane and methanol (1:1 ratio). Among all the formulations, the ternary ASD systems consisting of drug, polymer, and surfactant have resulted in improved release profiles. However, the ability of the surfactants to

maintain the stability of the formulations varied across the surfactants. The formulations with span 85 and TPGS have resulted in the complete release of the drug with no recrystallization. The formulations with span 20 and Tween 80 have resulted in incomplete release profiles and induced crystallization of the drug. The formulations with SDS have resulted in around 80% of drug release with no recrystallization. Among all the investigated surfactants, span 20 and TPGS have resulted in smaller particle sizes of 1 micron. Overall, span 85 has resulted in stable formulation with complete drug release profiles. No correlation was observed between the properties of the surfactants and the crystallization of the drug.

Sugandha Saboo et al., (2021) [86] investigated the effect of surfactants on the release profiles and stability of ASDs developed by rotaflash evaporation. The solution of physical mixtures is prepared in a 1:1 ratio of dichloromethane and methanol. Felodipine was selected as a model drug, and Kollidon VA 64 was selected as a polymeric carrier. The concentration of surfactant (TPGS) was maintained identical at 5 %w/w for all the formulations. Upon investigation of formulations for in vitro drug release profiles, the binary formulations consisting of drug and polymer have resulted in faster release profiles of only up to 20% of drug loading. Whereas incorporation of surfactant has resulted in improved kinetics of release profiles up to a concentration of 35% drug loading. The size of the ASD nanoparticles was found to be ranging between 200 - 300 nm. The presence of surfactant has prevented recrystallization of the drug, and the formulations of ternary mixtures consisting of drug, polymer, and surfactant were found to be stable for 12 hours when exposed to 100 %RH conditions. This shows the role of surfactant in aiding the release kinetics and stability of supersaturated drug solution.

4. Conclusion

In recent years ASDs have been most widely investigated for improving the solubility of poorly water-soluble drug substances. Various manufacturing strategies such as HME, spray drying, kinetisol are being employed for developing ASD systems. However, the stability of the amorphous drug remains to be a major challenge for developing ASD systems. The poor stability of amorphous drugs limits the drug loading resulting in an increased volume of the dosage form affecting patient compliance. Various factors, such as poor miscibility, drug-polymer interactions, and storage conditions, play a crucial affecting the stability of ASDs. Apart from the physical stability of ASDs, the recrystallization of drugs when present in a supersaturated state is another challenge affecting the performance of ASD formulations. In recent years, the incorporation of surfactant into binary mixtures of drug and polymer is being most widely investigated to prevent the solution-mediated recrystallization of drugs. However, still, a lot of research is warranted to establish the selection criteria of the surfactants.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The author declare that they have no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] Singh A, Worku ZA, van den Mooter G (2011) Oral formulation strategies to improve solubility of poorly water-soluble drugs. *Expert Opin Drug Deliv* 8:1361–1378
- [2] Singh D, Bedi N, Tiwary AK (2017) Enhancing solubility of poorly aqueous soluble drugs: critical appraisal of techniques. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Investigation* 2017 48:5 48:509–526
- [3] Eedara B, Nyavanandi D, Narala S, Veerareddy P, Bandari S (2021) Improved dissolution rate and intestinal absorption of fexofenadine hydrochloride by the preparation of solid dispersions: In vitro and in situ evaluation. *Pharmaceutics* 13:310
- [4] Chaudhari S, Dugar R (2017) Application of surfactants in solid dispersion technology for improving solubility of poorly water soluble drugs. *J Drug Deliv Sci Technol* 41:68–77

- [5] Lima ÁAN, Sobrinho JLS, Corrêa RAC, Neto PJR (2008) Alternative technologies to improve solubility of poorly water soluble drugs. *Latin American Journal of Pharmacy* 27:789–797
- [6] Sharma A, Jain C (2011) Solid dispersion: A promising technique to enhance solubility of poorly water soluble drug. *International Journal of Drug Delivery*
- [7] Tran P, Pyo Y, Kim D, Lee S, Kim J, Park J (2019) Overview of the manufacturing methods of solid dispersion technology for improving the solubility of poorly water-soluble drugs and application to anticancer drugs. *Pharmaceutics* 11:132
- [8] Tiwari R v., Patil H, Repka MA (2016) Contribution of hot-melt extrusion technology to advance drug delivery in the 21st century. *Expert Opin Drug Deliv* 13:451–464
- [9] Simões M, Pinto R, Simões S (2019) Hot-melt extrusion in the pharmaceutical industry: toward filing a new drug application. *Drug Discov Today* 24:1749–1768
- [10] Madan S, Madan S (2012) Hot melt extrusion and its pharmaceutical applications. *Asian J Pharm Sci* 7:123–133
- [11] Cunha-Filho M, Araújo MR, Gelfuso GM, Gratieri T (2017) FDM 3D printing of modified drug-delivery systems using hot melt extrusion: A new approach for individualized therapy. *Ther Deliv* 8:957–966
- [12] Santos J dos, Silveira Da Silva G, Velho MC, Carlos R, Beck R (2021) Eudragit®: A Versatile Family of Polymers for Hot Melt Extrusion and 3D Printing Processes in Pharmaceutics. *Pharmaceutics* 13:1424
- [13] Melocchi A, Parietti F, Maroni A, Foppoli A, Gazzaniga A, Zema L (2016) Hot-melt extruded filaments based on pharmaceutical grade polymers for 3D printing by fused deposition modeling. *Int J Pharm* 509:255–263
- [14] Seem T, Rowson N, Ingram A, Huang Z, Yu S, Matas M, Gabbott I, Reynolds G (2015) Twin screw granulation—A literature review. *Elsevier Powder Technology* 276:89–102
- [15] Maniruzzaman M, Nokhodchi A (2016) Continuous manufacturing via hot-melt extrusion and scale up: regulatory matters. *Drug Discov Today* 22:340–351
- [16] Patil H, Kulkarni V, Majumdar S, Repka M (2014) Continuous manufacturing of solid lipid nanoparticles by hot melt extrusion. *Int J Pharm* 471:153–156
- [17] Genina N, Hadi B, Löbmann K (2018) Hot melt extrusion as solvent-free technique for a continuous manufacturing of drug-loaded mesoporous silica. *J Pharm Sci* 107:149–155
- [18] Pawar J, Narkhede R, Amin P, Tawde V (2017) Design and Evaluation of Topical Diclofenac Sodium Gel Using Hot Melt Extrusion Technology as a Continuous Manufacturing Process with Kolliphor® P407. *AAPS PharmSciTech* 18:2303–2315
- [19] Mishra S, Richter M, Mejia L, Sauer A (2022) Downstream Processing of Itraconazole: HPMCAS Amorphous Solid Dispersion: From Hot-Melt Extrudate to Tablet Using a Quality by Design Approach. *Pharmaceutics* 14:1429
- [20] Mathers A, Pechar M, Hassouna F, Fulem M (2022) API solubility in semi-crystalline polymer: Kinetic and thermodynamic phase behavior of PVA-based solid dispersions. *Int J Pharm* 623:121855
- [21] Fan W, Zhu W, Zhang X, Xu Y, Di L (2019) Application of the combination of ball-milling and hot-melt extrusion in the development of an amorphous solid dispersion of a poorly water-soluble drug with. *RSC Adv* 9:22263–22273
- [22] Giri BR, Kwon J, Vo AQ, Bhagurkar AM, Bandari S, Kim DW (2021) Hot-melt extruded amorphous solid dispersion for solubility, stability, and bioavailability enhancement of telmisartan. *Pharmaceutics* 14:73
- [23] Khairnar S v, Pagare P, Thakre A, Rajeevan Nambiar A, Junnuthula V, Abraham MC, Kolimi P, Nyavanandi D, Dyawanapelly S (2022) Review on the Scale-Up Methods for the Preparation of Solid Lipid Nanoparticles. *Pharmaceutics* 14:1886
- [24] Janssens S, van den Mooter G (2009) Review: Physical chemistry of solid dispersions. *Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmacology* 61:1571–1586
- [25] Kennedy M, Hu J, Gao P, et al (2008) Enhanced bioavailability of a poorly soluble VR1 antagonist using an amorphous solid dispersion approach: A case study. *Mol Pharm* 5:981–993
- [26] Andrews G, AbuDiak O, Jones D (2010) Physicochemical characterization of hot melt extruded bicalutamide-polyvinylpyrrolidone solid dispersions. *J Pharm Sci* 99:1322–1335

- [27] Alonzo DE, Gao YI, Zhou D, Mo H, Zhang GGZ, Taylor LS (2011) Dissolution and precipitation behavior of amorphous solid dispersions. *J Pharm Sci* 100:3316–3331
- [28] Konno H, Handa T, Alonzo D, Taylor L (2008) Effect of polymer type on the dissolution profile of amorphous solid dispersions containing felodipine. *European Journal of Pharmaceutics and Biopharmaceutics* 70:493–499
- [29] Marsac PJ, Li T, Taylor LS (2009) Estimation of drug-polymer miscibility and solubility in amorphous solid dispersions using experimentally determined interaction parameters. *Pharm Res* 26:139–151
- [30] Rumondor ACF, Stanford LA, Taylor LS (2009) Effects of polymer type and storage relative humidity on the kinetics of felodipine crystallization from amorphous solid dispersions. *Pharm Res* 26:2599–2606
- [31] Ambike A, Mahadik K, Paradkar A (2005) Spray-dried amorphous solid dispersions of simvastatin, a low Tg drug: in vitro and in vivo evaluations. *Pharm Res* 22:990–998
- [32] Qian F, Huang J, Hussain M (2010) Drug-polymer solubility and miscibility: stability consideration and practical challenges in amorphous solid dispersion development. *J Pharm Sci* 99:2941–2947
- [33] Teja SB, Patil SP, Shete G, Patel S, Kumar Bansal A (2013) Drug-excipient behavior in polymeric amorphous solid dispersions. *Journal of Excipients and Food Chemicals* 4:70–94
- [34] Baghel S, Cathcart H, O'Reilly N (2016) Polymeric amorphous solid dispersions: a review of amorphization, crystallization, stabilization, solid-state characterization, and aqueous solubilization of. *J Pharm Sci* 105:2527–2544
- [35] Azs D Emuth B, Farkas A, Balogh A, et al (2016) Lubricant-induced crystallization of itraconazole from tablets made of electrospun amorphous solid dispersion. *J Pharm Sci* 105:2982–2988
- [36] Vo A, Zhang J, Nyavanandi D, Bandari S, Repka M (2020) Hot melt extrusion paired fused deposition modeling 3D printing to develop hydroxypropyl cellulose based floating tablets of cinnarizine. *Carbohydr Polym* 246:116519
- [37] Bandari S, Nyavanandi D, Kallakunta V, Janga K, Sarabu S, Butreddy A, Repka M (2020) Continuous twin screw granulation—An advanced alternative granulation technology for use in the pharmaceutical industry. *Int J Pharm* 580:119215
- [38] Narala S, Nyavanandi D, Srinivasan P, Mandati P, Bandari S, Repka M (2021) Pharmaceutical Co-crystals, Salts, and Co-amorphous Systems: A novel opportunity of hot-melt extrusion. *J Drug Deliv Sci Technol* 61:102209
- [39] Butreddy A, Nyavanandi D, Narala S, Fischer A, Bandari S (2021) Application of hot melt extrusion technology in the development of abuse-deterrent formulations: An overview. *Curr Drug Deliv* 18:4–18
- [40] Nyavanandi D, Kallakunta V, Sarabu S, Butreddy A, Narala S, Bandari S, Repka M (2021) Impact of hydrophilic binders on stability of lipid-based sustained release matrices of quetiapine fumarate by the continuous twin screw melt granulation technique. *Advanced Powder Technology* 32:2591–2604
- [41] Narala S, Nyavanandi D, Alzahrani A, Bandari S, Zhang F, Repka MA (2022) Creation of Hydrochlorothiazide Pharmaceutical Cocrystals Via Hot-Melt Extrusion for Enhanced Solubility and Permeability. *AAPS PharmSciTech*. <https://doi.org/10.1208/S12249-021-02202-8>
- [42] Alzahrani A, Nyavanandi D, Mandati P, Youssef A, Narala S, Bandari S, Repka M (2022) A systematic and robust assessment of hot-melt extrusion-based amorphous solid dispersions: Theoretical prediction to practical implementation. *Int J Pharm* 624:121951
- [43] Nyavanandi D, Mandati P, Narala S, Alzahrani A, Kolimi P, Pradhan A, Bandari S, Repka M (2022) Feasibility of high melting point hydrochlorothiazide processing via cocrystal formation by hot melt extrusion paired fused filament fabrication as a 3D-printed cocrystal. *Int J Pharm* 628:122283
- [44] Alzahrani A, Narala S, Youssef A, Nyavanandi D, Bandari S, Mandati P, Almotairy A, Almutairi M, Repka M (2022) Fabrication of a shell-core fixed-dose combination tablet using fused deposition modeling 3D printing. *European Journal of Pharmaceutics and Biopharmaceutics* 177:211–223
- [45] Dhoppalapudi Siddharatha (2022) Considerations in the formulation of amorphous solid dispersions by hot melt extrusion. *GSC Biological and Pharmaceutical Sciences* 21:012–021
- [46] Konda K, Dhoppalapudi S (2022) A Review of Various Manufacturing Approaches for Developing Amorphous Solid Dispersions. *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics* 12:189–200

- [47] Dhoppalapudi S, Illa N (2022) A review of hot melt extrusion paired fused deposition modeling three-dimensional printing for developing patient centric dosage forms. *GSC Biological and Pharmaceutical Sciences* 21:065–079
- [48] Siddharatha Dhoppalapudi, Prashanth Parupathi (2022) Hot melt extrusion: A single-step continuous manufacturing process for developing amorphous solid dispersions of poorly soluble drug substances. *GSC Advanced Research and Reviews* 13:126–135
- [49] Mamidi H (2019) Nanosponge as versatile carrier systems - an updated review. *Research Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* 8:20–28
- [50] Mamidi H, Rohera B (2021) Material-Sparing Approach using Differential Scanning Calorimeter and Response Surface Methodology for Process Optimization of Hot-Melt Extrusion. *J Pharm Sci* 110:3838–3850
- [51] Mamidi H, Rohera B (2021) Application of thermodynamic phase diagrams and Gibbs free energy of mixing for screening of polymers for their use in amorphous solid dispersion formulation of a. *J Pharm Sci* 110:2703–2717
- [52] Mamidi H, Mishra S, Rohera B (2021) Application of modified SeDeM expert diagram system for selection of direct compression excipient for liquid formulation of Neusilin® US2. *J Drug Deliv Sci Technol* 64:102506
- [53] Mamidi H, Mishra S, Rohera B (2019) Determination of maximum flowable liquid-loading potential of Neusilin® US2 and investigation of compressibility and compactibility of its liquid blends with PEG. *J Drug Deliv Sci Technol* 54:101285
- [54] Mamidi H, Palekar S, Nukala P, Mishra S, Patki M, Fu Y, Supner P, Chauhan G, Patel K (2021) Process optimization of twin-screw melt granulation of fenofibrate using design of experiment (DoE). *Int J Pharm* 593:120101
- [55] Bandari S, Nyavanandi D, Dumpa N, Repka M (2021) Coupling hot melt extrusion and fused deposition modeling: Critical properties for successful performance. *Adv Drug Deliv Rev* 172:52–63
- [56] Mamidi H (2017) Establishment of Design Space for Direct Compression of PEG (400) Loaded Neusilin® US2 by Modified SeDeM Expert System. St. John's University
- [57] Mamidi H (2021) Preformulation Studies for the Preparation of Amorphous Solid Dispersions. St. John's University
- [58] Mamidi HK, Mishra SM, Rohera BD (2017) Application of SeDeM diagram to improve the mechanical properties of powdered solutions.
- [59] Szabo E, Za P, Breckska niel, et al (2021) Comparison of amorphous solid dispersions of spironolactone prepared by spray drying and electrospinning: The influence of the preparation method on the. *Mol Pharm* 18:317–327
- [60] Balogh A, Farkas B, Farkas A, Szabó B, Démuth B, Kristóf Nagy Z, Marosi G (2018) Homogenization of amorphous solid dispersions prepared by electrospinning in low-dose tablet formulation. *Pharmaceutics* 10:114
- [61] Casian T, Borbás E, Ilyés K, et al (2019) Electrospun amorphous solid dispersions of meloxicam: Influence of polymer type and downstream processing to orodispersible dosage forms. *Int J Pharm* 569:118593
- [62] Becelaere J, Van E, Broeck D, et al (2022) Stable amorphous solid dispersion of flubendazole with high loading via electrospinning. *Journal of Controlled Release* 351:123–136
- [63] Démuth B, Farkas A, Pataki H, et al (2017) Detailed stability investigation of amorphous solid dispersions prepared by single-needle and high speed electrospinning. *Int J Pharm* 498:234–244
- [64] Dă B, Farkas A, Szabó B, et al (2017) Development and tableting of directly compressible powder from electrospun nanofibrous amorphous solid dispersion. Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apt.2017.03.026>
- [65] Nagy Z, Balogh A, Démuth B, et al (2015) High speed electrospinning for scaled-up production of amorphous solid dispersion of itraconazole. *Int J Pharm* 480:137–142
- [66] Yu D, Yang J, Branford-White C, Lu P, Zhang L, Zhu L (2010) Third generation solid dispersions of ferulic acid in electrospun composite nanofibers. *Int J Pharm* 400:158–164
- [67] Karanth H, Shenoy VS, Murthy RR (2006) Industrially feasible alternative approaches in the manufacture of solid dispersions: A technical report. *AAPS PharmSciTech*. <https://doi.org/10.1208/PT070487>
- [68] Paudel A, Geppi M, van den Mooter G (2014) Structural and dynamic properties of amorphous solid dispersions: the role of solid-state nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy and relaxometry. *J Pharm Sci* 103:2635–2662

- [69] Pandi P, Bulusu R, Kommineni N, Khan W, Singh M (2020) Amorphous solid dispersions: An update for preparation, characterization, mechanism on bioavailability, stability, regulatory considerations and marketed products. *Int J Pharm* 586:119560
- [70] Marano S, Barker S, Raimi-Abraham B, Missaghi S, Rajabi-Siahboomi A, Craig D (2016) Development of micro-fibrous solid dispersions of poorly water-soluble drugs in sucrose using temperature-controlled centrifugal spinning. *European Journal of Pharmaceutics and Biopharmaceutics* 103:84–94
- [71] Keen JM, LaFountaine JS, Hughey JR, Miller DA, McGinity JW (2018) Development of Itraconazole Tablets Containing Viscous KinetiSol Solid Dispersions: In Vitro and In Vivo Analysis in Dogs. *AAPS PharmSciTech* 19:1998–2008
- [72] Ellenberger DJ, Miller DA, Kucera SU, Williams RO (2018) Improved Vemurafenib Dissolution and Pharmacokinetics as an Amorphous Solid Dispersion Produced by KinetiSol® Processing. *AAPS PharmSciTech* 19:1957–1970
- [73] Ellenberger DJ, Miller DA, Kucera SU, Williams RO (2018) Generation of a Weakly Acidic Amorphous Solid Dispersion of the Weak Base Ritonavir with Equivalent In Vitro and In Vivo Performance to Norvir Tablet. *AAPS PharmSciTech* 19:1985–1997
- [74] LaFountaine JS, McGinity JW, Williams RO (2016) Challenges and Strategies in Thermal Processing of Amorphous Solid Dispersions: A Review. *AAPS PharmSciTech* 17:43–55
- [75] LaFountaine J, Jermain S, Prasad L, Brough C, Miller D, Lubda D, McGinity J, Williams R (2016) Enabling thermal processing of ritonavir–polyvinyl alcohol amorphous solid dispersions by KinetiSol® dispersing. *European Journal of Pharmaceutics and Biopharmaceutics* 101:72–81
- [76] Tian Y, Jacobs E, Jones D, McCoy C, Wu H, Andrews G (2020) The design and development of high drug loading amorphous solid dispersion for hot-melt extrusion platform. *Int J Pharm* 586:119545
- [77] Sarode A, Sandhu H, Shah N, Malick W, Zia H (2013) Hot melt extrusion (HME) for amorphous solid dispersions: predictive tools for processing and impact of drug–polymer interactions on supersaturation. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* 48:371–384
- [78] Ding Z, Wang X, Wang L, Zhao Y, Liu M, Liu W, Han J, Prakash S, Wang Z (2022) Characterisation of spray dried microencapsules with amorphous lutein nanoparticles: Enhancement of processability, dissolution rate, and storage stability. *Food Chem* 383:132200
- [79] Lang B, Liu S, McGinity JW, Williams RO (2016) Effect of hydrophilic additives on the dissolution and pharmacokinetic properties of itraconazole-enteric polymer hot-melt extruded amorphous solid dispersions. *Drug Dev Ind Pharm* 42:429–445
- [80] Liu X, Lu M, Guo Z, Huang L, Feng X, Wu C (2012) Improving the chemical stability of amorphous solid dispersion with cocrystal technique by hot melt extrusion. *Pharm Res* 29:806–817
- [81] Baghel S, Cathcart H, O'Reilly NJ (2018) Investigation into the Solid-State Properties and Dissolution Profile of Spray-Dried Ternary Amorphous Solid Dispersions: A Rational Step toward the Design and Development of a Multicomponent Amorphous System. *Mol Pharm* 15:3796–3812
- [82] Correa Soto CE, Gao Y, Indulkar AS, Ueda K, Zhang GGZ, Taylor LS (2022) Impact of Surfactants on the Performance of Clopidogrel-Copovidone Amorphous Solid Dispersions: Increased Drug Loading and Stabilization of Nanodroplets. *Pharm Res* 39:167–188
- [83] Deshpande TM, Shi H, Pietryka J, Hoag SW, Medek A (2018) Investigation of Polymer/Surfactant Interactions and Their Impact on Itraconazole Solubility and Precipitation Kinetics for Developing Spray-Dried Amorphous Solid Dispersions. *Mol Pharm* 15:962–974
- [84] Schittny A, Philipp-Bauer S, Detampel P, Huwyler J, Punschkov M (2020) Mechanistic insights into effect of surfactants on oral bioavailability of amorphous solid dispersions. *Journal of Controlled Release* 320:214–225
- [85] Indulkar AS, Lou X, Zhang GGZ, Taylor LS (2022) Role of Surfactants on Release Performance of Amorphous Solid Dispersions of Ritonavir and Copovidone. *Pharm Res* 39:381–397
- [86] Saboo S, Bapat P, Moseson DE, Kestur US, Taylor LS (2021) Exploring the role of surfactants in enhancing drug release from amorphous solid dispersions at higher drug loadings. *Pharmaceutics* 13:735.